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A MODERN VIEW OF THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE GOUT ATTACK (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract.

Gout is a chronic joint disease caused by the deposition of sodium urate crystals in and around the joint tissues. Gout is the most common arthropathy caused by the deposition of salts in the joints. Patients with gout experience a significant negative impact on their quality of life. During an acute attack of gout, patients experience severe joint pain, redness of the skin around the joint, and swelling. Treatment consists of two aspects: lifestyle modification and medical therapy.

Keywords: *gout, acute gout attack, joint, treatment, colchicine*

Materials and Methods: A literature review was conducted based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. Information on modern methods of conservative treatment of acute gout attacks was analyzed.

The purpose of the work is to analyze the literature and identify current methods of conservative treatment of acute gout.

Relevance. Gout is an inflammatory disease caused by the accumulation of excess urate crystals (sodium urate) in joint fluid, cartilage, bones, tendons, bursae, and other places [1].

Unlike most mammals, humans do not have an enzyme that can break down uric acid. Humans have much higher concentrations of urate and this is associated with the occurrence of certain clinical conditions, such as gout [2].

In developed high-income countries, the prevalence of gout ranges from 3% to 6% in men and from 1% to 3% in women. In 2015 and 2016, the incidence of gout was 3.9% among US adults (2.7% in women and 5.2% in men) [3].

Risk factors for gout include overweight, obesity, hypertension, excessive alcohol consumption, diuretics, and a diet rich in meat, seafood, and high-fructose foods [1,3].

Consumption of foods rich in purines is a risk factor for gout. These include meat products and certain

types of fish (e.g. anchovies, sardines, scallops, mussels).

Among alcoholic beverages, beer consumption is associated with an increased risk of gout compared to wine or spirits.

The use of a loop diuretic or thiazide diuretic can also lead to the development of gout [3].

There are two important factors that affect the concentration of uric acid in the body. These are the amount of uric acid produced and the excretion of uric acid from the body. Approximately two-thirds is excreted by renal clearance, and one-third by intestinal clearance [2].

Uric acid crystals precipitate faster at lower temperatures, so the fingers, toes, elbows and ears are the main sites of gout exacerbation and deposition of uric acid crystals in soft tissues (gouty tophi). Uric acid crystals can also be deposited in the urinary system (urolithiasis).

Precipitated uric acid crystals lead to the activation of inflammation in monocytes and the subsequent release of various inflammatory mediators, such as interleukin-1.

If untreated, an acute gout attack lasts from 3 days to 2 weeks. In 90% of cases, the first attack of gout in a patient is monoarthritis, most often inflammation of the joint at the base of the big toe (almost 70% of cases) [3,4]. Other joints, including the midfoot (25% to 50%), ankle (18% to 60%), upper limb (13% to 46%), and

interphalangeal joints (6% to 25%) can also be involved in the pathological process [4].

During a gout attack, patients experience swelling and severe joint pain, a condition known as acute gouty arthritis. In some patients, the frequency and duration of acute attacks increase over time and lead to chronic gout [1].

Results and discussion: Treatment of gout includes both lifestyle modification and pharmacological therapy [1]. Lifestyle modification consists of increasing exercise and reducing excess weight [1,4]. Changes in diet and lifestyle can reduce uric acid levels by almost 20%. Drug therapy for acute gout is aimed at the rapid resolution of pain and the disappearance of joint inflammation [4].

The role of nutrition in maintaining adequate serum uric acid levels is well established. However, it is not only the consumption of meat products and alcohol that play a role. It is difficult to clearly identify all the nutrients that play a role in the etiopathogenesis of the disease. However, there are numerous studies in the literature that report a relationship between serum vitamin C concentrations and uric acid.

It has been shown that high serum vitamin C levels have a positive effect on purine metabolism and help reduce uric acid levels, thus reducing the risk of sodium urate crystal deposition in the joints [5].

The treatment of acute gout attacks is mainly based on non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), colchicine and glucocorticoids.

However, there is refractory gout, which has persistent clinical manifestations, characterised by an inability to reduce serum uric acid concentrations below the target level of 6.0 mg/dl, increased urate deposition and tophi formation, as well as chronic inflammatory arthritis, and persistent symptoms of recurrent flares. Patients with refractory gout often respond poorly to these drugs or have contraindications [6].

Colchicine

Studies have shown that colchicine reduces pain in patients with gout flares. Lower doses of colchicine (initial dose of 1.2 mg, followed by 0.6 mg after 1 hour) have been found to be as effective as higher doses (1.2 mg, followed by 0.6 mg/h for 6 hours), which is important in preventing gastrointestinal complications. Colchicine is also associated with other gastrointestinal side effects, including nausea, vomiting, cramps, and headache [1]. Colchicine in therapeutic doses may cause side effects in patients with certain risk factors. The main ones are the use of concomitant medications and renal dysfunction. Colchicine is a substrate of both CYP3A4 and P-glycoprotein (P-gp). Inhibitors or competing substrates of CYP3A4 or P-gp increase the risk of colchicine toxicity. These include calcium channel blockers, azole antifungals, protease inhibitors, macrolide antimicrobials, tacrolimus, tamoxifen, cyclosporine, and amiodarone. A 1.8 mg dose of colchicine over 1 hour reduced pain compared to placebo [7]. Higher doses of colchicine (4.8 mg for 6 hours or 1 mg followed by 0.5 mg every 2 hours until complete response or no side effects) also improved pain control compared to placebo and resulted in fewer

side effects [8]. The 2012 American College of Rheumatology guidelines for the treatment of gout state that low-dose colchicine is not inferior to NSAIDs and corticosteroids for the treatment of acute gout. In severe acute gout, colchicine can be used with NSAIDs or corticosteroids [9]. The recommended maximum dose of colchicine is 1.2 mg/day for patients with creatinine clearance >50 ml/min and 0.6 mg/day for patients with creatinine clearance from 10 to 50 ml/min [7].

NSAIDs. A study was conducted with the drug tenoxicam, which was taken by gout patients 40 mg once a day. It was shown to reduce pain but was no different from placebo in terms of swelling in patients with acute gout attacks. There are studies that have shown that the use of NSAIDs to prevent gout attacks during urate-reducing therapy has a successful outcome. The main side effect of NSAIDs is gastrointestinal complications, ranging from minor (dyspepsia) to serious (ulcers and bleeding). Long-term use of higher doses can cause chronic renal failure [1].

Corticosteroids. High-quality indirect evidence suggests that systemic corticosteroids reduce pain in patients with acute gout. Although there has been no direct evidence to evaluate the effectiveness of systemic corticosteroids in the treatment of gout, corticosteroids have a proven anti-inflammatory effect. However, long-term use of corticosteroids is associated with side effects such as dysphoria, mood disorders, increased blood glucose levels, immune suppression, and fluid retention [1]. Intra-articular injection of corticosteroids is also recommended as a first-line treatment for acute gout attacks [10].

Allopurinol is a first-line urate-lowering drug. It is a purine analogue that competitively inhibits xanthine oxidase, reducing the production of uric acid. Allopurinol therapy should not be discontinued in the event of an acute gout attack; it can be safely started during an acute attack. In patients with normal renal function, allopurinol should be started at a dose of 100 mg per day for the first month. The daily dose should be increased by 50 mg every 2-4 weeks until the target serum uric acid concentration is reached [2].

The maximum recommended daily dose of allopurinol ranges from 300 to 900 mg, and the daily initial dose recommended for patients with normal renal function ranges from 50 to 200 mg [10].

Conclusion: Thus, the main drugs for the treatment of acute gout attacks are colchicine, NSAIDs and glucocorticoids. When using colchicine, it is necessary to pay attention to its side effects, incompatibility with some other medications and consider the possibility of prescribing small doses to reduce side effects.

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